

Supporting Information

Birth and Growth of Octapod-Shaped Colloidal Nanocrystals Studied by Electron Tomography

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1. Synthesis of Cu_{2-x}Se nanocrystals

Colloidal Cu_{2-x}Se nanocrystals were synthesized under nitrogen atmosphere. A solution prepared by mixing 0.039 g of Se (0.5 mmol) with 3 ml of oleylamine was heated to 150°C under vacuum using a standard Schlenk line for 1 h. The line was later switched to nitrogen flow and the temperature was raised to 230°C and kept there for 1 h until the Se was dissolved. This mixture was then cooled down and kept at 100°C. Separately, in a second flask anhydrous CuCl (0.099 g, 1 mmol) was added to a mixture of 5 ml of oleylamine and 5 ml of 1-octadecene. After pumping to vacuum for 1 h at 80°C using a standard Schlenk line, also this second flask was put under constant nitrogen flow. The temperature was then set to 300°C. When the reaction mixture temperature reached this value the Se-oleylamine mixture was injected into the reaction vial. The overall reaction time after injection was 15 min, after which the flask was cooled to room temperature. Then 5 ml of toluene were added to the reaction mixture, and the resulting mixture was then transferred to a glove box, where it was washed twice by repeated precipitations (via addition of ethanol) and re-dissolved in toluene. After the last precipitation step the particles were dissolved in 3 ml of trioctylphosphine (TOP).

2. Synthesis of CdSe(core)/CdS(pods) octapods

As-prepared Cu_{2-x}Se nanocrystals were used as seeds to synthesize CdSe(core)/CdS(pods) octapod-shaped nanoparticles in a one-step approach via cation exchange followed by pod growth. In the glove box, a solution was prepared which contained sulfur (16 mg) dissolved in TOP (0.5 g) and the previously synthesized Cu_{2-x}Se seeds, the latter in a known amount ($0.3 \cdot 10^{-9}$ mol of particles). This solution was injected into a reaction flask containing a mixture of surfactants (3 g trioctylphosphine oxide, 80 mg hexylphosphonic acid, 290 mg octadecylphosphonic acid) and 60 mg of CdO heated to 350°C. Due to the presence of Cd phosphonate complexes and the strong affinity of Cu to bind to phosphonic acids (stronger than for Cd), the cubic Cu_{2-x}Se nanocrystals were transformed into CdSe nanocrystals via a rapid cation exchange step. The cation exchange was followed by the CdS pod growth (both steps occurring consecutively in a one pot reaction after the above mentioned injection). For the first octapod sample (referred to as the “baby” octapods in the manuscript), an aliquot was

extracted from the reaction flask 2 minutes after the injection of the solution containing the Cu_{2-x}Se nanocrystals and the sulfur precursor into the hot solution of surfactants and the Cd precursor. After 10 minutes (for the sample labeled “sample 1” in the manuscript) or 7 minutes (for the sample labeled “sample 2” in the manuscript) the reaction mixture was cooled down to room temperature and the particles were precipitated by using methanol and dissolved in toluene. Different batches of seeds were used for the two batches of octapods (samples 1 and 2) which might also induce slight differences in the shapes and dimensions of the final particles.

3. HRTEM analysis of 2 minutes aliquots

HRTEM images of “baby” octapods in suitable orientations show that opposite wurtzite CdS pods share the same crystallographic orientation.

Figure SI-1: HRTEM image of a “baby” octapod in an aliquot collected after 2 min from the start of the CdS growth synthesis, highlighting the formation of CdS pods with flat ends (F) or tips (T). Higher magnification images from two opposite pods, both identically oriented along the $[5\ 2\ \bar{7}\ 3]$ zone axis of CdS, are shown in the insets. The structure of the CdSe core is not visible due to the superposition of the CdS pods on the CdSe core.

4. EFTEM analysis of CdSe(core)/CdS(pods) octapods

EFTEM images of “grown-up” octapods of sample 2 show a selenium-containing region in the central part of the particles and allow to determine the average size of the Se-containing core of the octapods.

Figure SI-2: Combination of EFTEM elemental maps of S (L edge at 165 eV, 20 eV slit width) and Se (L edge at 1436 eV, 20 eV slit width) acquired with the three-windows method on a group of “grown-up” octapods of the sample 2 (see manuscript), all oriented approximately along the <100> of the sphalerite CdSe core. The average lateral edge size l of the Se-containing core is 12 ± 1 nm.

Attached files:

Movie SI-1.avi. Rotation of a 2 minutes aliquot reconstructed by electron tomography.

Movie SI-2.avi. Clipping of a reconstructed octapod of sample 1 (see manuscript) perpendicular to a <111> direction of its CdSe core, showing the sequential sectioning of the particle.